

VIBRATION CONTROL OF ACTIVE STRUCTURES WITH PIEZOELECTRIC MODAL SENSORS AND ACTUATORS

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SUMMARY: The finite element method (FEM) is applied to model the sensing and actuating mechanism of piezoelectric sensors and actuators. With the aid of Independent Modal Space Control (IMSC) method, optimal design of vibration control of active structures is performed. And the controllability and observability conditions for single mode are presented. Based on the IMSC method, a new set of modal sensor and actuator is proposed which consist of several piezoelectric patches. Although they are to some extent approximate when compared to those developed by Lee and Moon[1], design and application of them are much simpler. Numerical results are presented to illustrate the feasibility of the developed approximate modal sensors and actuators.

KEYWORDS: piezoelectric material, modal sensor and actuator, optimal control, vibration suppression, finite element method

INTRODUCTION

Due to the two characteristics, i.e. the direct and the inverse piezoelectric effects, piezoelectric materials have been widely used as sensors and actuators in the area of smart structures. Extensive research has been done to understand and model the sensing and actuating mechanisms. Analytical models of piezoelectric sensors and actuators embedded in or surface-bonded on smart beams, plates, and shells are proposed by numerous researchers (see, for example, [2-4]). And the finite element method[5-7] is shown to be the most rigorous way to analyze the piezoelectric structures.

Application of the piezoelectric smart structures into vibration suppression has been demonstrated to be a feasible way not only numerically but also experimentally. Optimal design of the vibration control with piezoelectric smart sensors and actuators is highly desirable [8-10]. Moreover, it is well known that, in a closed-loop control system, observation spillover may bring about unstable dynamic response of undamped structures and control spillover may excite uncontrolled residual modes. To avoid these phenomena, Lee and Moon [1] introduced modal sensors and actuators for one dimensional piezoelectric structures, which can monitor and actuate specified modes. However, design of them is much complicated. And their application is limited to structures of simple and regular appearance. In this paper, the Independent Modal Space Control (IMSC) method is employed to perform the optimal control. And the controllability and observability of specified modes for surface-

bonded piezoelectric structures is proposed. After designing the sensing and control algorithms, a new type of modal sensor and actuator is achieved. Implementation of the developed modal sensors and actuators into structures is much simple. Numerical results are presented to show the feasibility of the modal sensors and actuators.

FINITE ELEMENT DISCRETION

The motion equation of a plate-type active structure with surface-bonded piezoelectric sensors and actuators can be modeled by the following finite element equations [7]

$$\begin{aligned} [M]\{\ddot{x}\} + [K_{uu}]\{x\} - [K_{u\phi}]\{\phi\} &= \{F_m\} \\ [K_{\phi u}]\{x\} + [K_{\phi\phi}]\{\phi\} &= -\{Q\} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\{x\}$ is the generalized nodal displacement vector, $\{\phi\}$ the element voltage vector of piezoelectric patches, $[M]$ and $[K_{uu}]$ the mass and the elastic stiffness matrices, $[K_{\phi u}]$ and $[K_{u\phi}]$ the electric-mechanical coupling matrices, $[K_{\phi\phi}]$ the dielectric matrix, and $\{F_m\}$ and $\{Q\}$ are, respectively, the mechanical force vector and the external applied electric free charge vector acting on piezoelectric element. It should be noted that, in Eq. (1), the electric potential of every point on the surface of piezoelectric element is assumed to have a same value. Moreover, each piezo patch is modeled by a layer of a finite element in this paper. Therefore, for an active element (i.e. an element has a surface-bonded piezoelectric patch), an electric voltage variable must be included in the generalized mechanical displacement vectors.

SENSING AND ACTUATING EQUATIONS

With the aid of Eq. (1), the sensing and/or actuating equations of a piezoelectric patch can be obtained readily. When the patch is acted as a sensor (via the direct piezoelectric effect), as we know, no free charge density is applied on the major surfaces (edge surface are negligible). Consequently, the induced electric charge is

$$Q^e = [K_{\phi u}^e]\{x^e\} \quad (2)$$

And the corresponding induced electric voltage of the active element due to deformation is

$$\phi^e = -[K_{\phi\phi}^e]^{-1}[K_{\phi u}^e]\{x^e\} \quad (3)$$

Eqs. (2) and (3) constitute the sensing equations of a piezoelectric element.

On the other hand, the piezoelectric element may be used as actuator (through the inverse piezoelectric effect). And both the external free charge and electric voltage can be acted as driving signals to be imposed on the surface of the element. When the driving signal is the free charge, the deformation equation of the active structure is obtained by substituting Eq. (1b) into (1a), i.e.

$$[M^e]\{\ddot{x}^e\} + [K_{uu}^e]\{x^e\} = \{F_m^e\} + [K_{u\phi}^e][K_{\phi\phi}^e]^{-1}(-\{Q^e\} - [K_{\phi u}^e]\{x^e\}) \quad (4)$$

And when electric voltage is applied on the surface of actuator, the induced deformation equation is much simple

$$[M^e]\{\ddot{x}^e\} + [K_{uu}^e]\{x^e\} = \{F_m^e\} + [K_{u\phi}^e]\{\phi^e\} \quad (5)$$

Eqs. (3)-(5) are the sensing and actuating formulations on element level and they can be assembled into global ones.

OPTIMAL CONTROL

In order to achieve optimal control, the linear second order equations (1) are usually transformed into the state equation of first order. After introducing a quadratic performance index, one can obtain the control algorithm by minimizing the index function, i.e. solving a matrix Riccati equation. However, for a real structure, the degree of freedom is so large that solution of the derived matrix Riccati equation is time-consuming and impracticable expensive. Independent Modal Space Control (IMSC) method is shown to be more preferable, in which it is assumed that each mode can be controlled separately [9-10]. Instead of solving matrix equation, only a set of uncoupled algebraic equations is needed to be solved in IMSC. And it is introduced briefly in this paper.

Without losing generality, the closed-loop feedback control equation of a active structure can be written as,

$$[M]\{\ddot{x}\} + [K_{uu}]\{x\} = \{F\} \quad (6.)$$

where $\{F\}$ is the termed as control force vector and will be determined by IMSC.

With the modal transformation technique,

$$\{x\} = [\Psi]\{y\} \quad (7.)$$

one can rewrite Eq. (6) into a set of uncoupled equations in the modal space, that is,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{y}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \ddot{y}_n \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \omega_1^2 & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \omega_n^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} y_1 \\ \vdots \\ y_n \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ \vdots \\ f_n \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8.)$$

where n is the number of natural modes, ω_i the eigenfrequency, and f_i is the modal control force given by

$$f_i = \{\varphi_i\}^T \{F\} \quad (9.)$$

in which $\{\varphi_i\}$ is the i th modal vector.

In IMSC, the modal control force f_i is assumed to have the form of

$$f_i = -(g_{1i}\omega_i y_i + g_{2i}\dot{y}_i)/r \quad (10.)$$

where r is a weight factor and g_{1i} and g_{2i} are given by

$$\begin{aligned} g_{1i} &= -\omega_i r + \sqrt{(\omega_i r)^2 + \omega_i^2 r} \\ g_{2i} &= \sqrt{2r\omega_i \left(-r\omega_i + \sqrt{(r\omega_i)^2 + r\omega_i^2} \right) + r\omega_i^2} \end{aligned} \quad (11.)$$

Eqs. (11) are obtained by minimizing the following performance index

$$J = \int_0^\infty \omega_i^2 y_i^2 + \dot{y}_i^2 + r f_i^2 dt \quad (12.)$$

in which the first term, the second term, and the third term of right hand side of Eq. (12) refer to the potential energy, the kinetic energy, and the control effort, respectively.

Controllability and observability of the IMSC have been studied by Hughes and Skelton [11] and Laub and Arnold [12]. In this paper, however, only the controllability and observability

of specified modes are considered. Since for structure control, only those modes are of most interest.

The closed-loop feedback control system of piezoelectric active structures is illustrated in Fig. 1. And each patch shown in it is a self-sensing actuator [13], which means a piezo element is used simultaneously as a sensor as well as an actuator. Although both the electric charge and electric voltage can be sensed and then be fed back to act as driving signal, the induced electric charge is outputted as sensed signal while electric voltage is imposed on the actuator to drive it in this paper. Moreover, both constant velocity feedback controller and

constant position feedback controller are employed. Therefore, the sensing electric charge and driving voltage have the form of, respectively,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Q_1^e \\ \vdots \\ Q_{N_p}^e \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{K_{\phi u}^e\}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \{K_{\phi u}^e\}_{N_p} \end{Bmatrix} \{x\} \quad (13.)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \phi_1^e \\ \vdots \\ \phi_{N_p}^e \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} & \cdots & G_{1N_p} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ G_{N_p 1} & \cdots & G_{N_p N_p} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_1^e \\ \vdots \\ Q_{N_p}^e \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{G}_{11} & \cdots & \tilde{G}_{1N_p} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \tilde{G}_{N_p 1} & \cdots & \tilde{G}_{N_p N_p} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{Q}_1^e \\ \vdots \\ \dot{Q}_{N_p}^e \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14.)$$

where subscript N_p is the number of piezoelectric elements, $[G]$ and $[\tilde{G}]$ the feedback gain matrices to be determined, ϕ_i^e the feedback voltage acting on the i th piezoelectric element, and Q_i^e is the sensing charge of the i th piezoelectric element. G_{ij} and \tilde{G}_{ij} having the meaning of that the sensed charge of j th piezo element is fed back to control the i th piezoelectric element.

When electric voltage is acted as feedback signal, the control force is

$$\{F\} = \left[\begin{Bmatrix} \{K_{\phi u}^e\}_1^T & \cdots & \{K_{\phi u}^e\}_{N_p}^T \end{Bmatrix} \right] \begin{Bmatrix} \phi_1^e \\ \vdots \\ \phi_{N_p}^e \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15.)$$

Substituting Eq. (15) into (9) yields the modal control force

$$f_i = \{\varphi_i\}^T [K_{u\phi}] \{\phi\} \quad (16.)$$

For a given piezoelectric active structure, the modal vector $\{\varphi_i\}$ and the coupling matrix $[K_{u\phi}]$ are prescribed. Following Eq. (16), we can see that the i th mode is uncontrollable if the following express exists

$$\{\varphi_i\}^T [K_{u\phi}] = \mathbf{0} \quad (17.)$$

Actually, Eq. (17) is also the sufficient condition of the unobservability of the i th mode for a piezoelectric active structure. Combining Eq. (17) and (13), we have

$$\{Q\} = [K_{\phi u}] \{x\} = [K_{\phi u}] \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq i}}^n \{\phi_k\} y_k \quad (18.)$$

which implies that the i th mode is unobservable.

MODAL SENSOR AND ACTUATORS

In a distributed structural control system, it is highly desirable that sensors only monitor those modes to be controlled. However, in reality, those sensors also respond to those uncontrolled residual modes from which observation spillover can introduce unstable dynamic response of undamped structures. At the same time, for certain cases, only single mode or a group of natural modes need to be controlled (such as vibration excited noise control). Modal sensors can also be used to identify which mode plays a primary role in the motion of a structure, then a corresponding modal actuator can be adopted to control the motion. An adaptive structure can thus be developed. To these ends, Lee and Moon [11] proposed spatially distributed modal sensors and actuators. Because the modal sensors and actuators depend on the shape of the master structures, the design of them is much complicated, i.e. for one-dimensional structures (e.g. beam and ring) the shape design of them is two-dimensional while for two-dimensional structures it is three-dimensional. As a result, application of them is limited to structures of simple form.

Figure 2 Illustration of the modal sensor

In the following part, a different type of modal sensors and actuators are proposed through the feedback gain design instead of shape design. The modal sensor shown in Fig. 2 consists of several piezo patches, and its output electric charge is defined as

$$Q_m = \{G_s\}^T \begin{Bmatrix} Q_1^e \\ \vdots \\ Q_{N_p}^e \end{Bmatrix} \quad (19.)$$

Substituting Eq. (13) into (19) produces

$$Q_m = \{G_s\}^T [K_{\phi u}] \{x\} \quad (20.)$$

Combining Eqs. (8) and (20), the modal sensor output has the form of

$$Q_m = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_p} G_{sj} [K_{\phi u}^j] \{\phi_i\} \right) y_i \quad (21.)$$

When $\{G_s\}$ is chosen such that for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_p} G_{sj} [K_{\phi u}^j] \{\phi_i\} = \begin{cases} \alpha_i, & i = k \\ 0, & i \neq k \end{cases} \quad (22.)$$

where α_i is an arbitrarily chosen constant. The k th modal sensor is then developed, that is,

$$Q_m = \alpha_k y_k \quad (23.)$$

If the modal sensor is to monitor a group modes, e.g. mode m_1, m_2, \dots , and m_p , Eq. (22) should be replaced by

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_p} G_{sj} [K_{\phi u}^j] \{\varphi_i\} = \begin{cases} \alpha_i, & i = m_1, m_2, \dots, m_p \\ 0, & i \neq m_1, m_2, \dots, m_p \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

Since the number of piezoelectric patches is fewer compared to that of natural modes, Eqs. (22) or (24) can not be satisfied exactly. There are several ways to evaluate the linear algorithm $\{G_s\}$ in Eqs. (22) or (24). Conventionally, the generalized pseudo inverse method can give a reliable solution. In view of structure control, the equations on the lowest N_p modes in Eqs. (22) or (24) are chosen to be satisfied in this paper (i.e., the mode truncation method is employed). Solution of Eqs. (22) or (24) can then be obtained.

In addition to modal sensors, modal actuators can be formulated in a similar way. Substituting Eq. (14) into Eq. (15), we get the control force vector of the closed loop feedback control system as,

$$\{F\} = [K_{u\phi}] \left([G][K_{\phi u}] \{x\} + [\tilde{G}][K_{\phi u}] \{\dot{x}\} \right) \quad (25)$$

Then, the modal actuating force can be written as

$$f_i = \{\varphi_i\}^T [K_{u\phi}] \left([G][K_{\phi u}] \sum_{k=1}^n \{\varphi_k\}^T y_k + [\tilde{G}][K_{\phi u}] \sum_{k=1}^n \{\varphi_k\}^T \dot{y}_k \right) \quad (26)$$

in which n is the number of natural modes.

Comparing Eq. (26) with (11) yields

$$\{\varphi_i\}^T [K_{u\phi}] [G] [K_{\phi u}] \{\varphi_k\}^T = \begin{cases} -g_{1i} \omega_i / r, & k = i \\ 0, & k \neq i \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

$$\{\varphi_i\}^T [K_{u\phi}] [\tilde{G}] [K_{\phi u}] \{\varphi_k\}^T = \begin{cases} -g_{2i} / r, & k = i \\ 0, & k \neq i \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Similar to the modal sensors in the previous part, there are $N_p \times N_p$ unknowns in Eqs. (27) and (28) while the number of equations to be satisfied is $n \times n$. And the feedback gain matrices $[G]$ and $[\tilde{G}]$ are determined by choosing $N_p \times N_p$ relations in Eqs. (27) and (28) concerning the modes of most interest in structure control.

The modal sensor and modal actuator developed herein are to some extent approximate. It is obvious inferior to those proposed by Lee and Moon [1]. However, the present modal sensor and actuator make the application of them into complex structures become possible.

Table 1 Material properties of piezoelectric material and the elastic plate

	E (Pa)	ν (Poisson ratio)	ρ (Kg/m³)	d_{31} (CN⁻¹)
elastic plate	73.0×10 ⁹	0.3	2630	
piezoelectric material	63.0×10 ⁹	0.35	7600	37.0×10 ⁻¹¹

Table 2 The first eight natural frequencies of the plate

mode	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
frequency (Hz)	11.0	71.8	152.5	212.1	362.0	440.7	484.6	768.1

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to illustrate the feasibility of the proposed modal sensor and actuator, a cantilevered plate with surface-bonded piezoelectric patches is studied, shown in Fig. 3. A sinusoidal force is applied at the middle point of the free end to excite the plate. The plate is modeled by 4×10 shear deformable plate elements. The finite element code developed by Chen *et al.* [7] is adopted to simulate the optimal control.

The material properties of piezoelectric material and the elastic plates are given in Table 1. Table 2 lists the natural frequencies of the cantilevered plate without piezo patches. It should be noted that the 1st, the 2nd, and 4th modes are deflection modes, 3rd mode the twist mode, and 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th modes are hybrid modes. In this paper, eight and three patches, shown in Fig. 4, are used to simulate the modal sensor and actuator, respectively. Fig. 5 presents the frequency response curves of modal sensors which monitor single mode or a group of modes. Since the modal sensors shown here are made up of only eight patches, they are, in general, approximate. And observation spillover occurs when the frequency is above 700 Hz. Fortunately, the response at high frequency is not of most importance in structure control. And the spillover can be avoided by several methods, such as low frequency filter.

Figure 3 A cantilevered plate and its finite element mesh

Figure 4 displacement of the piezoelectric patches

Figure 5 Frequency characteristics of the modal sensors

Figure 6 Frequency characteristics of the modal actuators

Application of modal actuators to control single mode is illustrated in Fig. 6. The deflection magnitude is the deflection of the free end along the axial direction. As we can see that the modal actuators can give viable control for specified modes.

From the above results, we can conclude that the developed modal sensors and actuators have the ability to monitor and actuate specified modes. And the application of them into complex structure is much easy although the host structure studied in this paper is quit simple, e.g. a plate. With the modal sensors and actuators, an adaptive structure is easy to make into practice: a structure can identify its motion in accordance with the output of modal sensors, and then select a corresponding modal actuator to control it motion.

However, it should be noted that the developed modal sensor and actuator depend strongly on the modal information and it is implicitly assumed that the modes are distinctive. Therefore, further study of it should be performed investigate how the design the modal sensors and actuators when the obtainable mode information is not sufficiently exact and repeated eigenfrequencies exist.

REFERENCES

1. Lee, C.K. and Moon F.C., "Modal sensors/actuators", ASME J. Appl. Mech., Vol. 57, 1990, 434-441
2. Crawly, E.F. and de Luis J., "Use of piezoelectric actuators as elements of intelligent structures", AIAA J., Vol. 25, 1987, 1373-1385
3. Wang, B.T. and Rogers, C.A., "Laminated plate theory for spatially distributed induced strain actuators", J. Composite Mater., Vol. 25, 1991, 433-452
4. Tzou, H.S. and Gadre, M., "Theoretical analysis of a multilayered thin shell coupled with piezoelectric shell actuators for distributed vibration controls", J. Sound Vib., Vol. 132, 1989, 433-450
5. Chandrashekhara, K. and Agarwal, A.N., "Active vibration control of laminated composite plates using piezoelectric devices: A Finite Element Approach", J. Intel. Mater. Syst. and Struct., Vol. 4, 1993, 496-508
6. Hwang, W.S. and Park, H.C., "Finite element modeling of piezoelectric sensors and actuators", AIAA J., Vol. 31, 1993, 930-937
7. Chen, C.Q., Wang, X.M. and Shen, Y.P., "Finite element approach of vibration control using self-sensing piezoelectric actuators", Comput. and Struct., Vol. 60 (3), 1996b, 505-513
8. Baz, A. and Poh, S., "Performance of an active control system with piezoelectric actuators", J. Sound Vib., Vol. 126 (2), 1988, 327-343
9. Khot, N.S., Oz, H., and Grandhi, R.V., "Optimal structure design with control gain norm constraint", AIAA J., Vol. 29 (12), 1988, 2047-2053
10. Lammering, R., Jia, J.H. and Rogers, C.A., "Optimal placement of piezoelectric actuators in adaptive truss structures", J. Sound Vib. Vol. 171 (1), 1994, 67-85
11. Hughes, P.C. and Skelton R.E., "Controllability and observability of linear matrix second order systems", ASME J. Appl. Mech., Vol. 47, 1980, 415-420
12. Laub, A.J. and Arnold, W.J., "Controllability and Observability criteria for multivariable linear second-order models", IEEE Trans. Automat. Contr., Vol. AC-29 (2), 1994, 163-165
13. Garcial, E., Dosch, J., and Inman, J., "The application of smart structure to the vibration suppression problem", J. Intell. Mater. Syst. and Struct., Vol. 3, 1992, 659-667